

DEFORMATION AND FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITE FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Continuous macroscopic carbon nanotube (CNT) fibers are made of meso-scale CNT bundles, where most CNTs are well aligned along the fiber axis direction. Super-stretchable helical composite fibers made from the pure CNT fibers are promising candidates for applications in stretchable and wearable devices. This paper presents multi-scale molecular dynamic simulations of CNT fibers and super-stretchable helical composite fibers. Simulations of monotonic and cyclic tensile tests were conducted to study their plastic deformation and micro-structural evolution. It is found that the elongation of the helical structures can reach 100%~300%, depending on the pitch of the helix and the tensile strain rate. The specific strength of the helical structures greatly decreases for a decreasing helix pitch. The deformation mechanisms are divided into four types according to different predominate factors, for different strain rates. Besides, the reinforcing mechanism of the composite fibers is illustrated. Dependence of the mechanical behaviour on the microstructure of the composite fibers under different strain rates is revealed as well. Furthermore, the variations of mechanical properties of the composite fibers with cycle numbers under relatively low load are predicted.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotube (CNT) fibers have attracted enormous attention due to their hierarchical structure that transfers the superior properties of the individual CNTs at nanoscale to macroscale and realizes novel applications, such as torsional actuators [1] and sensors [2]. One of the most attractive macroscopic structures is one-dimensional CNT fibers. High-performance CNT fibers are currently produced by various methods, including wet spinning of CNT fibers from CNT dispersions in solutions, and dry spinning of CNT fibers from well-aligned CNT arrays or directly from CNT aerogels. Recently, Wu et al. [3] reported a method for continuously producing spring-like CNT fibers and stated that the maximum tensile strength of the spring is 325 MPa and the tensile strain is up to 213%. In addition to high strength, CNT fibers have good flexibility which is required in many applications, such as artificial muscles. For further enhancing of the CNT fibers, polymers with different molecular structures and sizes have been employed in the post-spin process. According to the experimental results, CNT/polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) composite fibers exhibit significant reinforcement of mechanical properties than the neat CNT fibers. Liu et al. [4-6] proposed an effective method of making high-strength CNT based composite fibers by using a super aligned CNT fiber as a framework and then inserting PVA into the inter-tube spaces of the framework to enhance the strength of yarns. The as-produced CNT/PVA composite yarns possess very high tensile strengths up to 2.0 GPa and Young's moduli more than 120 GPa. The enhancement of these composite fibers is mainly attributed to the cross-link network of the polymer chains that help enhancing the load transfer between the CNTs and their bundles and ameliorating their interfacial slippage.

2 METHOD AND MODELS

In this paper, the mechanical behavior of as-spun CNT fibers and the helical structures of CNT/polymer composite fibers are studied by performing coarse-grained molecular dynamics (CGMD) simulations, focusing on their deformation behavior and damage mechanism, and the roles of helical geometric structural and the polymer chains. Coarse-grained (CG) models with structure and force potentials derived from the full-atom MD simulation results can provide both reasonable

computational precision and efficiency simultaneously. Moreover, in CGMD simulations, the microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of materials are obtained strictly based on the variation of total potential energy of the system, and are varied with different force field parameters and structures of the materials.

In the CG model of CNTs, deformation of the CNTs are described by the change of the spring length and spring angle. Moreover, a finite extensible nonlinear spring is introduced to fit the actual force-strain response of the CNTs. Besides, the elongation limit of the CNT spring is taken as 27 per cent in the present work. Furthermore, CG model for the PVA polymer used in this work is also based on all-atom simulations, with force fields developed by using the program YASP reported by Reith et al. Models of amorphous PVA were obtained from Accelrys Material Studio. All the MD simulations were performed using the massively parallelized modelling code LAMMPS.

Then, a schematic view of the preparation of a dry-spun CNT/polymer composite fiber and its helical structure is shown in Fig. 1. At first, a continuous CNT sheet is pulled out from a CNT array grown on a substrate, and densified into a CNT fiber. Then, polymer droplets are continuously applied at the end of the CNT fiber for enhancement. At last, the CNT/polymer composite fiber is rotated further to obtain a macroscopic helical structure. Considering this process, the present modelling starts from the infiltration of the CNT/polymer composite fiber. The detailed modelling method is explained below.

Figure 1: Multi-scale modeling of CNT/PVA composite fibers.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rate-dependent mechanical behaviours of the CNT/PVA composite fibers were studied. Stress-strain curves of the CNT/PVA composite fiber at different strain rates are plotted in Fig. 2. As the strain rate increases, the specific strength of the composite fiber increases due to increased bond stretching energy. Under the strain rate of 0.005 ps^{-1} , as presented in Fig. 3a, only slippages of CNT bundles are discovered in the composite fiber during the tension process. With the increasing of strain, some adjacent CNT bundles are separated from each other, causing the final failure of the composite. Besides, slowly loosening of the outer polymer layer is induced during the tensile process. Then, at strain rate of 0.01 ps^{-1} (Fig. 3b), slippages of the CNT bundles take place until the strain reaches 0.36 owing to the first breakages of the CNT bundles. Thereafter, the broken CNT bundles are drawn apart under tensile loading, causing greater deformation of the polymer chains around the cracks than that of the other chains. At last, when the strain rate is increased to 0.05 ps^{-1} , as plotted in Fig. 3c, multiple breakages generate in the CNT bundles at a relatively small strain of 0.28, and develop gradually with the increasing strain. The microstructural evolution of the inner CNT bundles and the outer polymers are coupled in response to the tensile loading. Stretching and slipping of the CNT bundles as well as stretching and loosening of the polymers make up the whole deformation of the CNT/PVA composite fiber at lower strain rates, while breakages of CNT bundles dominate the deformation of the CNT/PVA composite fibers at higher strain rates.

Figure 2: Stress-strain relations of CNT/PVA composite fibers at different strain rates.

Figure 3: Microstructural evolution of CNT/PVA composite fiber under monotonic tensile loading at different strain rates.

Then, tensile tests were carried out on the helical CNT/PVA composite fibers. The tensile stress-strain curves are plotted in Fig. 4. Here, we use values of helical pitch to represent different helical structures. It is seen from the stress-strain curves that the stretchability of the helical composite fibers are significantly improved compared to the straight composite fibers. Furthermore, the ultimate strain of the helical composite fibers increased with decreasing helix pitch, though this is accompanied by a concomitant reduction in specific strength. When the helix pitch is decreased to 33 nm, the ultimate strain of the helical composite fiber can reach 160% based on our simulations. Another essential point is that the characteristics of the stress-strain curves also vary with the helix pitches. Because the pitch is greater than or equal to 60 nm, the stress-strain curve is almost linear; yet as the helix pitch is decreased, the stress-strain curves become nonlinear and characterized by strain hardening.

Figure 4: Tensile stress-strain curves of a straight CNT/PVA composite fiber and helical CNT/PVA composite fibers with different helix pitches at a strain rate of 5×10^{-5} /ps.

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